

Studia breviora

Additional material of *Buteo spassovi* Boev & Kovachev, 1998 from the Upper Miocene locality Hadzhidimovo (Blagoevgrad region, SW Bulgaria)

Several avian taxa of the Upper Miocene locality of *Hipparion* fauna, located near the town of Hadzhidimovo (Blagoevgrad region, SW Bulgaria), have been found to date: *Buteo spassovi* (Boev & Kovachev, 1998); *Circaetus rhodopensis* (Boev, 2012); *Falco bulgaricus* (Boev, 2011); *Euroceros bulgaricus* (Boev & Kovachev, 2007); and *Struthio karatheodoris* (Boev & Spassov, 2009; Boev *et al.*, 2008). The present paper aims to represent a new find of a medium-sized accipitrid, comparable in size to the two hitherto established species, *Buteo spassovi* and *Circaetus rhodopensis*, from the same locality and horizon.

Spassov's buzzard (*Buteo spassovi* Boev & Kovachev, 1998) was described based on a nearly complete tibiotarsus excavated by the late amateur paleontologist Dimitar Kovachev (1928–2013). The new find described herein was given for examination by Assoc. Prof. Latinka Hristova (NMNHS-BAS) (see Fig. 1a–e). It is still the only fossil species of buzzard known from SE Europe. The taxonomy used herein follows that of Thiollay (1994) and Dickinson and Remsen Jr. (2013). The osteological terminology is after Baumel and Witmer (1993). All measurements were taken using callipers to 0.1 mm accuracy. They are as follows: a) maximal width of distal epiphysis; b) diameter of condylus dorsalis; c) diameter of condylus ventralis; and d) minimal thickness of distal epiphysis in incisura intercondylaris (Fig. 2; see also Table 1). The examined specimen was compared with 19 specimens of eight West-Palaearctic accipitrids. ‘Smaller’, ‘much smaller’, ‘larger’ or ‘much larger’ used in the comparison section below mean that the fossil specimen differs significantly in size from the specimens of the com-

Fig. 1. *Buteo spassovi* NMNHS 18758 – humerus sin. dist.: medial view (a); lateral view (b); ventral view (c); dorsal view (d); caudal view (e). Scale bar – 1 cm. Photographs: Assen Ignatov.

Fig. 2. Measurements of the specimen NMNHS 18758.

pared species, and thus their taxonomic identity is excluded. The age assessment is after Mein (1990), *i.e.*, Late Miocene (Meotian, lower part; MN zone 11), >7.4 Ma.

The studied buzzard find represents a distal portion of a right humerus of an adult medium-sized accipitrid. It includes distal epiphysis and the distal

one-fifth of the diaphysis. The maximal total length of the preserved bone fragment is 32.2 mm. It is well petrified and mineralized. The medial surface of condylus ventralis is damaged. The entire fossa musculi brachialis is preserved. The color of the diaphysal part is light greyish, while the epiphysal part is light beige.

Circaetus gallicus is larger, with less protruded epicondylus dorsalis and more medially positioned fossa m. brachialis. *Clanga clanga* is larger, with less protruded epicondylus dorsalis and shallower fossa m. brachialis. *Clanga pomarina* is larger, with less protruded epicondylus dorsalis. *Pernis apivorus* displays shallower sulcus m. humerotricipitalis and less protruded epicondylus dorsalis. *Circus aeruginosus* has less concaved fossa olecrani, shallower sulcus m. scapulotricipitalis and less protruded epicondylus dorsalis. *Buteo rufinus* is smaller, with less protruded epicondylus dorsalis and more caudally positioned tuberculum supracondylare ventrale. *Buteo lagopus* has relatively longer fossa m. brachialis and sharper condylus ventralis in ventral view. *Buteo buteo* displays high similarity, with better-outlined fossa olecrani.

Comparisons made regarding the bone morphology, as well as the sizes of the specimens of all these

Table 1
Measurements of distal humerus of some West Palearctic medium-sized accipitrids (ref. to Fig. 2)

Species/specimens	a	b	c	d
Fossil specimen – Hadzhidimovo				
<i>Buteo spassovi</i> NMNHS 18 758	17.6	8.9	7.6	5.5
Recent				
<i>Buteo buteo</i> NMNHS 19/1986 Bulgaria	19.0	10.4	8.4	4.3
<i>Buteo buteo</i> NMNHS 23/1989 Bulgaria	18.5	10.1	8.2	4.7
<i>Buteo buteo</i> NMNHS 31/1992 Bulgaria	18.6	10.2	7.9	4.2
<i>Buteo lagopus</i> NMNHS 2/1987 Bulgaria	18.8	10.0	8.6	5.2
<i>Buteo lagopus</i> NMNHS 3/1987 Bulgaria	18.2	9.8	8.7	5.0
<i>Buteo lagopus</i> NMNHS 4/1989 Bulgaria	18.6	10.2	9.0	5.2
<i>Buteo rufinus</i> NMNHS 1/1989 Bulgaria	21.5	11.6	10.0	5.1
<i>Buteo rufinus</i> NMNHS 12/2008 Bulgaria	21.4	11.3	10.0	5.8
<i>Pernis apivorus</i> NMNHS 1/1989 Bulgaria	17.9	9.7	7.9	4.1
<i>Pernis apivorus</i> NMNHS 2/2014 Bulgaria	17.0	9.6	8.3	4.4
<i>Pernis apivorus</i> NMNHS 5/2014 Bulgaria	19.1	10.0	8.5	4.4
<i>Circus aeruginosus</i> NMNHS 1/1991 Bulgaria	16.4	10.5	7.5	4.6
<i>Circus aeruginosus</i> NMNHS 2/1993 Bulgaria	16.5	9.5	8.3	3.7
<i>Circus aeruginosus</i> NMNHS 4/2002 Bulgaria	16.7	8.8	8.1	3.5
<i>Clanga pomarina</i> NMNHS 3/1989 Bulgaria	23.1	13.8	10.7	5.8
<i>Clanga pomarina</i> NMNHS 4/1996 Bulgaria	23.2	12.1	10.9	5.5
<i>Clanga clanga</i> NMNHS 1/2010 Bulgaria	24.8	13.2	11.4	6.7
<i>Circaetus gallicus</i> NMNHS 1/1984 Bulgaria	26.2	13.8	11.9	6.2
<i>Circaetus gallicus</i> NMNHS 3/2016 Bulgaria	24.9	13.8	11.3	6.8

compared species, show the greatest similarity to *Buteo buteo*. As mentioned above, *Buteo spassovi* was described based on a single tibiotarsus. Therefore, the new find is tentatively referred herein to the same species. However, it corresponds both metrically and morphologically to the buzzard of the genus *Buteo*. Recently, a Late Miocene skeleton of *Buteo* sp. was published by Pavia *et al.* (2022), but the preservation of the Italian specimen did not allow further identification.

REFERENCES

- Baumel J.J., Witmer, L.M. 1993. 4 Osteologia. In: Baumel, J., King, A., Breazile, J., Evans, H., Vanden Berge, J. (Eds.), *Handbook of Avian Anatomy, Nomina Anatomica Avium*. Nuttall Ornithological Club 23, 45–132.
- Boev, Z. 2011. *Falco bulgaricus* sp. n. (Aves, Falconiformes) from the Middle Miocene of Hadzhidimovo (SW Bulgaria). *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 63 (1), 17–35.
- Boev, Z. 2012. *Circaetus rhodopensis* sp. n. (Aves, Accipitriformes) from the Late Miocene of Hadzhidimovo (SW Bulgaria). *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 64 (1), 5–12.
- Boev, Z., Kovachev, D. 2007. *Euroceros bulgaricus* gen. nov., sp. nov. from Hadzhidimovo (SW Bulgaria) (Late Miocene) – the first European record of Hornbills (Aves: Coraciiformes). *Geobios* 40 (1), 39–49, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geobios.2005.12.001>.
- Boev, Z., Kovachev, D. 1998. *Buteo spassovi* sp. n. – a Late Miocene buzzard (Accipitridae, Aves) from SW Bulgaria. *Geologica Balcanica* 29 (1–2), 125–129.
- Boev, Z., Spassov, N. 2009. First record of ostriches (Aves, Struthioniformes, Struthionidae) from the late Miocene of Bulgaria with taxonomic and zoogeographic discussion. *Geodiversitas* 31 (3), 493–507, <https://doi.org/10.5252/g2009n3a1>.
- Boev, Z., Spassov, N., Kovachev, D. 2008. First Remains of Fossil Ostriches (Aves: Struthioniformes – Struthionidae) from Bulgaria. *Acta Zoologica Bulgarica* 60 (1), 89–98.
- Dickinson, E.C., Reamsen Jr., J.V. (Eds). 2013. *The Howard & Moore Complete Checklist of the Birds of the World, 4th Edition, Vol. 1*. Aves Press, Eastbourne, UK, 461 pp.
- Mein, P. 1990. Updating of MN zones. In: Lindsay, E.H., Fahlbusch, V., Mein, P. (Eds), *European Neogene Mammal Chronology*. NATO ASI Series, Vol. 180, Springer, Boston, 73–90, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-4899-2513-8_6.
- Pavia, M., Cavagna, S., Pellegrino, I., Pellegrino, L., Carnevale, G. 2022. The oldest fossil record of *Buteo* (Aves, Accipitridae) from the Late Miocene of Italy and its evolutionary implications. *Bollettino della Società Paleontologica Italiana* 61 (2), 145–158.
- Thiollay, J.M. 1994. Family Accipitridae (Hawks and Eagles). In: del Hoyo, J., Elliot, A., Sargatal, J. (Eds), *Handbook of the Birds of the World, Vol. 2. New World Vultures to Guinea-fowl*. Lynx Edicions, Barcelona, 52–205.

Zlatozar Boev
National Museum of Natural History
Bulgarian Academy of Sciences
1000 Sofia, Bulgaria
e-mail: boev@nmnhs.com